

Micro Crack Resolution by Reverse Cutting Direction of Monocrystalline Wafers

Bryan Christian S. Bacquian

Central Engineering and Development NPI, Back-End Manufacturing & Technology, STMicroelectronics, Inc. Calamba City, Laguna, Philippines 4027

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I. OVERVIEW

- Wafers are typically formed by high purity mono crystalline material and their crystal structure are aligned to the surface on a relative direction called Miller Index
- As shown in Figure 1, chippings is mostly observed due to the cracking of these crystalline structures during mechanical dicing process, specifically thin dies.

Fig. 1. Chippings vs Silicon plane misalignment

II. PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION

- Wafers are typically sawn through by a mechanical diamond grit blades in order to grind silicon and successfully separate the so called “dies”
- However, chippings, typically observed caused by mechanical grinding happening during diamond and silicon friction during mechanical dicing process.

Fig. 2. Chippings occurred on a Conventional Mechanical Sawing.

III. PROCESS SOLUTION

- A new process parameter, reverse cutting direction, is developed to ensure the alignment of the crystalline structure by wafer to be on a same direction with the respect to blade entrance

Fig. 3. Cutting Direction change and Anova analysis between the existing and new cutting direction

- New Cutting direction have minimized the effect of backside chippings and reduced its standard deviation which help improved process capability of mechanical dicing process.
- Therefore reverse cutting direction have helped increased the process capability of mechanical dicing for thin die applications